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The New Age of Digital Evolution: Call to Be Human and Be Responsible

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Abstract: Evolution and innovation are two similar terms nowadays that can be understood as a synonym for transformation. Both are related to humankind as they move on history by bringing in the world a change that helps everyone to survive. In this age of information, the prominent concept of Artificial Intelligence has made many of the dreams of the past into reality at present. Indeed, the benefits of such innovations are not equitably shared in society as human beings are also undergoing an evolution in this digital age. In this digital age, therefore, true innovation is possible only if every person is an opportunity for transformation and every person becomes a responsibility of the other. In every possible manner, innovation should be understood today as a manner of interdependence in this digital era.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Sociality, Environment, Technology, Genetics, Digital Age

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Introduction

Although the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is making truly revolutionary breakthroughs, we have to put its progress in perspective with pros and cons. Moving forward from remote-controlled robots, our next goal is to design true automation, robots that have the ability to make their own decisions requiring only minimal human intervention. (Kaku, 2018) The profound shift in technology lifted civilization from the curse of ignorance and poverty and took us into the machine age. AI is concerned with building machines that can act and react appropriately, adapting their response to the demands of the situation. (Finlay, 1996) We, humans, have temporal consciousness in addition to spatial and social consciousness. However, we are constantly preparing for the future and even for beyond our own life spans. (Kaku, 2018) Now, it is high time to think of being human in this age.

Artificial Intelligence: Its Identity and Purpose

We can understand better the identity and purpose of AI enquiring its “Being for Others” and making a social critique of it.

Human Life: Being for the Other as the Purpose of AI

The duty of any human being as the social animal, as Aristotle says, is to be present in the need of the other. As they are part of a society, the relationships have always a role to play to bring together all of the members in your neighbourhood as well as in your families in order to identify and realize them as we see through a plane glass panel as your own brother or sister. Unlike all other life-forms on this planet, which must passively await their fate, we humans are masters of our own destiny. Fortunately, we are now creating the tools that will

defy the odds given to us by nature, so that we may don't become part of those life-forms destined for extinction. (Kaku, 2018) As products of a blind process of replication and selection, human beings as a whole – body and mind – differ only in degree of complexity from robots or machines. (Slingerland, 2008) The key to moving successfully through the world, according to Zhuangzi, a Chinese thinker, is simultaneously keeping both perspectives in mind, seeing the human in the light of the Heavenly and thus seeing through to its contingent nature, while at the same time acting in accordance with the constraints of being a human in the world of humans. (Slingerland, 2008)

Influence of AI in the Betterment of Agriculture

To be successful, AI innovations will need to overcome understandable human fears of being marginalized. AI will likely replace tasks rather than jobs in the near term, and will also create new kinds of jobs. But the new jobs that will emerge are harder to imagine in advance than the existing jobs that will likely be lost. Changes in employment usually happen gradually, often without a sharp transition, a trend likely to continue as AI slowly moves into the workplace. Many middle-aged workers have lost well-paying factory jobs and the socio-economic status in family and society that traditionally went with such jobs. *LinkedIn*, the popular social network for business people offers many advantages. *LinkedIn* makes it easy to find candidates who are not actively searching for work. (Tapscott, 2009) AI is combining information from global satellite imagery with the weather and agronomic data to help farmers improve crop yields, diagnose and treat crop disease and adapt to changing environments. This approach to

farming is known as precision agriculture and it can help increase farm productivity to feed more of the growing population.

Young people, and with them the entire world, are beginning to collaborate especially regarding environment through activists like Greta Thunberg. For the first time in history, young people have affordable, global, multimedia enabling them to research, collaborate and organize in order to bring about this needed change. Their hopes, determination, knowledge and facility with the Net are being applied to one of the greatest challenges which is to save the planet earth. (Tapscott, 2009)

AI and Its Educational Influence Today

Technology influences forms of learning. Computers, especially, Artificial Intelligence, facilitate a greater degree of collaborative learning through peer exchange and interaction among equals. Social networking sites provide an experiential space for actively taking on, rather than merely acting out, the trace of technology in the human self (Zylinska, 2013). The implications of digitization of print on literature, literary studies and research are only beginning to dawn upon scholars of literature. In the case of ‘real-time’ teaching, the instructor can use a projected image of a text. In a wired classroom, the instructor’s system can control all other systems. The electronic classroom will textualize classroom discourse (Nayar, 2004). Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) are essentially course delivery systems and generally include course materials, assessment facilities, conferencing and chat software. (Nayar, 2004). Internet databases such as *JSTOR* or *Project Muse* available on subscription enable students and researchers to access the full text of articles from major journals (Nayar, 2004).

Artificial Intelligence and Genetics

The gene by itself is inert, and can only express itself when located in a body. The human is seen as an expression of the gene, where the genetic code is the language that makes meaning in the form of human. Gene therapy is a medical intervention at the level of the cell and the molecule. It renders the body into increasingly smaller sections for analysis, but also for intervention and modification. Research rates have been high towards the advance in research, mainly in genetic engineering and immune suppressive therapy which has helped to improve survival chances greatly. Electrical and biochemical stimulations for neurological dysfunctions are also available. Gene therapy offers the potential of a one-time cure for inherited ailments and diseases. Nanomedicine is the application of nanotechnology to the treatment and prevention of disease. Genetic reprogramming enables the body to experience the world differently, especially when that body has been unable to do so previously due to corporeal problems or disease.

Being Human: Social Concern in the Present Age

The process of enhancing ourselves is not new but has been happening for all of human existence. Throughout history, we see examples of how humans have used artificial means to enhance our power and influence. In the future, we might live in the mental age, where our thoughts control the world around us. (Kaku, 2018) We do not normally associate machines with emotion. Indeed it is the ability to perform rationally, logically, without the baggage of emotional response that makes an intelligent machine powerful. Emotion is the mechanism by which we take account of shared human experience in our

decisions. The new sociality is based on contingency and immediacy, of shifting and altering loyalties. It is also based on information gathering, dispersal and appropriation of information.

Considering the relationships in the world today, mutual respect always has the prime concern. Respect for the person, therefore, means doing nothing contrary to personal either relative to the part of being the person already obtained or relative to the part which a person seeks to obtain (Rosmini, 1994). Sociality is based on social performances, communication and linkages. We present a self to the world, and the world responds to it. Although human beings can draw advantage for themselves both from the use of things and the use of persons, the use of things differs essentially and infinitely from the use of persons.

The notion of a good of a human being is not only a biological notion. Human welfare is associated with the satisfaction of needs and desires. In our society, training in skills and acquisition of knowledge are seen as components of the welfare of members of society. But choosing something by an individual must be aimed at the benefit of another person and that is the reason why we distinguish between self-regarding and other-regarding virtues (Smit, 2014).

A Social Critique on Artificial Intelligence

A social critique of AI is facilitated by exploring the virtual world first and then that of AI.

Virtual World: A Mirror which Makes You Self-Reliant

AI expert Rodney Brooks wrote, “My prediction is that by the year 2100 we will have very intelligent robots everywhere in our everyday lives. But we will not be apart from them – rather

we will be part robot and connected with the robots” (Kaku, 2018). Virtual reality need not be a prison. It can be the raft, the ladder and the transitional space. Virtual spaces may provide safety for us to expose what we are missing so that we can begin to accept ourselves as we are. We don’t have to reject life on the screen, but we don’t have to treat it as an alternative life either. We are all dreaming cyborg dreams, which means dreaming of a situation where man is in a machine. While children imagine morphing humans into metallic reptiles, our computer scientists dream themselves immortal (Turkle, 2002).

If a video game player has already merged with the computer, he is already a cyborg. It is an age where we feel fragmented and alone as individuals looking at the mirror would see themselves alone devoid of relations, even though we find many mythologies emerging to put the world back together again. The digital world is often disconnected or make us disconnected from many of the world’s problems by virtue of its members’ affluence and social standing. The blog or any form of New Media self-representation can be seen as an integral part of identity-making in the fragmented postmodern age. The digital young do need to develop coherent philosophies for responding to the very problems that the exhausted current system fails to address like racial hostility. The Digital Revolution or AI needs to offer solutions for eradicating poverty, ignorance and war in radical ways (Katz, 2002). Digital technologies free us from the constraints of space and place. As computers are able to perform more and more of the tasks currently performed by people, there will be less need for human-human contact. This shift from other people to reliance on machines may cause a

breakdown in social structures and social responsibility (Finlay, 1996).

Artificial Intelligence: A Wall Against the Other

In 1955, a select group of researchers met at Dartmouth and created the field of Artificial Intelligence. But they made a crucial mistake assuming that the human brain was a digital computer. The concept of AI as an area of science was more close to fiction. However, the idea of AI is no longer a fiction, but a reality that has become part of our daily lives (Poola, 2017). AI systems are still quite crude, and they are extraordinarily inept at many tasks that are accomplished with ease by a five-year-old human. Similarly, there is still only a mere understanding of how the body-brain serves even quite basic functions as memory, emotion and self-consciousness. (Slingerland, 2008) With AI, there has been the minimal occurrence of errors especially when typing since the computers can predict what we are going to write and make corrections.

People can get lost in virtual worlds. We must understand the dynamics of virtual experience both to foresee who might be in danger and to put these experiences to best use (Turkle, 2002). Reality is the result of our interface through the body's various senses of the physical world. In the digital age of AI this reality is 'mixed reality'. The body interfaces with the world in a different way today, and all reality is the mix of the virtual space of electronic communication and information. If the humans understand the right use of AI, a machine-oriented environment, and as language differentiates them from other animals, humans can become culture-creating and self-conscious creatures who evolve into moral beings knowing what is right and what is wrong. They should become rational

animals responsive to reasons considering the norms and values of society (Smit, 2014).

The electronic society is characterized by more adult-like children and more childlike adults; more career-oriented women and more family-oriented men. As we move forward in case of AI and technology, our society also spirals backwards. If AI is possible in machines then humans are reduced to little more than machines themselves. The middle and upper classes are moving towards the behaviours once associated with the illiterate lower classes. (Meyrowitz, 2002) To recognize the new paradigm of inter-being is not to deny the obvious truth that we perceive ourselves as separate, independent beings, but to understand that this separateness is an illusion. (Barash, 2018) The individual is not a destination. Every individual is a route to something more or something else. The new sociality is a series of proliferating paths rather than destinations. Humans are social animals and without considering the importance of relations in their life, they are easily drawn to loneliness. The use of mass media to relieve such loneliness is frequently found in modern society (Severin and Tankard, 2002).

Human Being as a Commodity Today

The rise of posthumanism as a philosophical paradigm, treating the human as co-evolving with the other species and refusing to treat the human body or consciousness as autonomous and sovereign has resulted in new views of the human itself. It shows how the human can always morph into something else, adapt to a device or a context. Posthumanism redefines the term 'nature'. When cloning, genetic engineering, nanomedicine, chip-implants alter the

human body, the distinction between ‘nature’ and synthetic break down at the interface because the synthetic is incorporated into the natural body and all bodies, therefore, become cyborgs.

Computers, globalization and Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have transformed contemporary culture. It has been in the realm of consumer culture which also considers every human being also as a commodity (Nayar, 2004). Mass culture, therefore, apparently erases true authenticity, autonomy and subjectivity of a human being. Utilitarianism which is the greatest good for the greatest number is unable to solve the problem of how justly to distribute the total good (Kauffman, 2014). Besides making people incapable of thinking and doing, the market-culture is taking away the power of decision as well. In this free world, we are not actually free to decide for ourselves. We can no more decide what to wear, what to eat and what to drink. Gradually even the very ability to think and to decide for ourselves is drained out from us (Puthenpurackal, 2015).

A Theological Critique of AI

The church is always against any method or technological advancement which affects human dignity like Artificial Reproductive Technology (ART). It can include anything from choosing the gender of children to women delaying the birth of the first child until after they have established their careers (Nayar, 2004). Cloning involves the use of genetic information from a single cell to create an entirely new human being. Gene therapy is the use of genetic manipulation for the treatment of disease. The aspect which is important in this Age of Reason is that we miss spirituality at a fundamental level. We give our faith to science and rationality. Our adoration of technology from washing machines to thousands of apps becomes the

strongest case among the neo-atheists, overconfident in their science to think that any belief in any form of God, monotheistic or not, is stupid. (Kauffman, 2014)

Question of Human Dignity facing AI Today

The quality of human life can be enhanced while human bodies and consciousness can be augmented through technology. The amount of time and energy people spend communicating or trying to do so, is stupendous and perhaps literally immeasurable. With the revolution in computer-assisted communication: e-mail, cell phones, texting, Twitter, Youtube and growing interest in understanding how these new modalities impact our ancient predilections, there are also new threats to privacy along with these electronic assists. (Barash, 2018) Artificial Reproductive Technology (ART), cloning and prosthetics alter the physiological and other processes of the body, thereby making these processes the effect of the human-machine interface.

AI for the New Millenium

As we are witnessing in the present age the vulnerability of human existence as an individual being and social being in keeping human relations today, I think in the light of theological and scientific introspection some suggestions can be made regarding the betterment of relationships in this Information Age of gadgets and supercomputers.

- There should be the assistance of AI in every field where the basic needs of people are not met with like food and shelter.
- Successful scientific experiments with the help of AI should be also influencing the rural people in the villages today.

- The mentality towards human dignity should be enhanced not considering human beings merely as a commodity.
- AI should be a great help in enhancing human life in the world today.
- AI can be a great help in different fields especially in the lives of the differently-abled in every possible manner.

Conclusion

Human beings are moving through Stone Age towards the Information Age where the money is no more visible but is flowing as liquid cash. Being human in the world is possible if the people are aiming at some good through a united effort. Even though Artificial Intelligence can be considered a boon in the various areas of current human and social

Even though Artificial Intelligence can be considered a boon in the various areas of current human and social development, strict monitoring is required where the dignity of the human being is tarnished.

development, strict monitoring is required where the dignity of the human being maybe tarnished. Every person, including Christians, have the responsibility to make the necessary steps to consider the human being as a neighbour and not the commodity of personal gratification. Humans can claim to have created a better world, and the world can claim to have made growth, only insofar as it gives greater light and better form to the humans in the society. To contemporary humans, it seems to be a disturbing reminder. The basic identity of human beings is radically questioned in the present world and if the humans give way to machines, the world as a living universe will remain an illusion. Now it is in our hands to explore or to enhance the world around us through our own hands and not rely exclusively on a machine or platform.

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